

Rare earth free e-drives
featuring low
manufacturing cost

ReFreeDrive

Rare earth free E-drives for electric vehicle application

T. Jezdinsky, European Copper Institute

G. Fabri, University of L'Aquila

ReFreeDrive Project Overview

13 partners, 6 European countries

Motor Design & Manufacturing

Power electronics

Vehicle integration & testing

Project coordination

Copper

UNIVERSITÀ
DEGLI STUDI
DE L'AQUILA

UNIVERSITÀ
DEGLI STUDI
DE L'AQUILA

OEM Validation

Steel

ReFreeDrive Project Overview

Why rare earth elements free solutions?

Supply risk

Cost

Market uncertainties

Environment & LCA

ReFreeDrive Project Overview

Why rare earth elements free?

SUPPLY RISK

Medium-Term (2015–2025) Criticality Matrix

U.S. Department Of Energy - Critical materials strategy - December 2011
https://www.energy.gov/sites/prod/files/DOE_CMS2011_FINAL_Full.pdf

ReFreeDrive Project Overview

Why rare earth elements free?

COST

Fig. 6. Materials cost in a 30 kW traction motor for a motor with rare earth magnets ('interior permanent magnet motor') and two options without [8].

ReFreeDrive Project Overview

Why rare earth elements free?

MARKET UNCERTAINTIES

<https://www.statista.com/statistics/450152/global-reo-neodymium-oxide-price-forecast/>

ReFreeDrive Project Overview

Why rare earth elements free?

J.D. Widmer et al. / Sustainable Materials and Technologies xxx (2015) xxx-xxx

ENVIRONMENT & LCA

J.D. Widmer, et al., Electric vehicle traction motors without rare earth magnets, (2015), <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2214993715000032?via%3Dihub>

ReFreeDrive Project Overview

What about **copper**? Not a critical raw material

Primary route: mining (~70% of demand)

Annual production
21 Mtonnes

Reserves
830 Mtonnes
(40 years)

Identified resources
2100 Mtonnes
(100 years)

Total resources
5000 Mtonnes
(250 years)

Deep sea deposits excluded

Secondary route: recycling (~30% of demand)

400 Mtonnes available
in the “urban mine”
(20 years)

Copper can be
recycled repeatedly
without downgrading

Most of copper
alloying elements can
be recovered

Diversified geographic
availability

Meeting future copper demand: <https://sustainablecopper.org/meeting-future-copper-demand/>

The World Copper Factbook 2018: <https://www.icsg.org/index.php/component/jdownloads/finish/170/2876>

Dynamic Analysis of Global Copper Flows. <https://pubs.acs.org/doi/10.1021/es400069b>

US Geological Survey (USGS), 2019: <https://prd-wret.s3-us-west-2.amazonaws.com/assets/palladium/production/s3fs-public/atoms/files/mcs-2019-coppe.pdf>

ReFreeDrive Project Overview

Project Objectives

- The main aim of this project is to develop **rare earth-free traction technologies**

**INDUSTRIAL
FEASIBILITY**

**MASS
PRODUCTION**

**LOWER
COSTS**

- Material selection
- Manufacturing processes
- Design optimisation
- Scalability

ReFreeDrive Project Overview

Project Technologies: we will design & manufacture 8 different e-motors for electrical powertrains

Induction machines with copper rotor

Fabricated
Die Cast

Synchronous reluctance machines

PMassisted
Without PM

75kW and 200kW

ReFreeDrive Project Overview

Target figures

**Benchmark
Tesla S60**

**30% INCREASE
SPECIFIC TORQUE**

**50% MOTOR
LOSSES REDUCTION**

**15% COST
REDUCTION**

**50% INCREASE
OF POWER DENSITY IN
POWER ELECTRONICS**

ReFreeDrive Project Overview

Please visit:
www.refreedrive.eu

and

ElectricDrivetrainInnovationCluster
in LinkedIn

LATEST NEWS

ReFreeDrive Project Overview

EV powertrains requirements

Electromagnetic Design

- Machine topology:
 - 4-pole, 36-slot, 50-bar
- Geometry:
 - OD = 190mm
 - L = 161mm
- Materials
 - M235-35A steel (rotor & stator)
 - CuAg0.04 (fabricated rotor cage)
 - Cu-ETP (die-casted rotor cage)
- Stator winding:
 - Turns / Phase = 12
 - Packing factor (%) = 73
- Power supply:
 - DC Voltage = 350V/720V
 - Current = 350Arms/500Arms

Torque-Efficiency Map

Power-Efficiency Map

Radial Geometry

Winding pattern

Thermal Design

- Series Cooling system:
- Stator jacket
- Rotor groove
- EWG 50/50
- Flow rate 10 l/min

ReFreeDrive Project Overview

PM assisted Synchronous Reluctance Motor

Design Characteristics:

- Distributed round wire windings;
- Optimized rotor geometry;
- Rare Earth Free Ferrite Magnets
- 10 poles, 60 stator slots

Parameter (unit)	KPI	ReFreeDrive
Specific peak power (kW/kg)	> 4.3	4.9
Peak power density (kW/lit)	> 8.0	22.6
Specific peak torque (Nm/kg)	> 8.2	9.5
Peak torque density (Nm/lit)	> 15.4	46.5
Maximum speed (rpm)	15000÷20000	17500
Peak efficiency (%)	> 96	96
Active parts weight (kg)	< 47	45.5

ReFreeDrive Project Overview

Pure SynRel motors

Motor Design

Pros:

- Simple stator (close to IM)
- cost effective rotor solution,
- no magnets no copper in the rotor
- No cooling issues in the rotor
- High Efficiency

Cons:

- Very challenging design for high speed
- Poor power factor
- Torque ripple

Machine topology:

- 6-pole, 54- stator slot
- Round wire windings

Geometry:

- OD = 220mm
- L = 200mm

Materials

- M235-35A steel (rotor & stator)

Power supply:

- DC Voltage = 350V/720V
- Current = 350Arms/635Arms

Rotor design aided by topology optimization

A. Credo, G. Fabri, M. Villani and M. Popescu, "Adopting the topology optimization in the design of high-speed synchronous reluctance motors for electric vehicles," *IEEE Transactions on Industry Applications*

A. Credo, G. Fabri, M. A. Villani and M. Popescu, "A Robust Design Methodology for Synchronous Reluctance Motors," in *IEEE Transactions on Energy Conversion*.

www.refreedrive.eu

Optimized for:

- low torque ripple,
- acceptable power factor
- High efficiency
- High speed

ReFreeDrive Project Overview

Pure SynRel motors

Performance

The design matches the challenging requirements

- Very wide speed range;
- High peak efficiency, good efficiency at low speed;
- Acceptable power factor;
- Interesting EV motor technology for less demanding application.

And the research continues...

- * active parts only
- + housing included
- # efficiency maps include mechanical losses

Parameter	unit	Tesla Model S	RFD Goals	SynRel design
Motor type		Induction Motor		SynRM
Cooling		Liquid		Liquid
Specific Peak Power (*)	kW/kg	3.3	> 4.3	5.3
Specific Peak Torque	Nm/kg	6.32	> 8.2	8.4
Maximum speed	krpm	14500	15000 ÷ 18000	18000
Peak efficiency	%	92	> 96	96
Active parts weight	kg	68	< 47	46
Motor dimensions (+): Total Length	mm	225	< 310	310

ReFreeDrive Project Overview

Power Electronics

Design Characteristics:

- SIC Based Power Electronics;
- Thin Film capacitors;
- Laminated DC bus bar;
- Integrated PE and motor cooling.

1200V rated Power modules provide a better specific power respect to lower voltage ratings (i.e. 750V).

Mitsubishi SIC Module
 FMF800DX-24A (1200V, 800 A)
 Cost: about 1500€ (few samples)
 Estimated cost in 2023:
 120€ (mass production-3€/kW PE)

Losses per device vs Frequency @ 200 kW

Laminated busbars

ReFreeDrive

ReFreeDrive Project Overview

SiC market

Power SiC device market Forecast by segment

(Source: CS Market Monitor, Yole Développement, Q4 2019)

ReFreeDrive Project Overview

Motors performance

Motor variant	Induction	Ferrite SynRel	Pure SynRel
DC-link voltage	720 V	720 V	720 V
Max. modulation	0.98	0.98	0.98
Max. current	500 Arms	636 Arms	636 Arms
Required inv. kVA	430 kVA	550 kVA	550 kVA
Peak torque	380 Nm	470 Nm	415 Nm
Maximum speed	20,000 rpm	18,000 rpm	18,000 rpm
Gear ratio	13.55	12.19	12.19
Peak overall power	300 kW	250 kW	290 kW
Peak power @nmax	150 kW	90 kW	80 kW

ReFreeDrive Project Overview

Efficiency over EPA cycle (Preliminary),
dual motor configuration with one motor fully loaded.

ReFreeDrive Project Overview

EV powertrains requirements

ReFreeDrive Project Overview

Prototyping steps

ReFreeDrive Project Overview

Next steps

December 2020

March 2021

Motor & Integrated powertrain testing

In-vehicle integration

ReFreeDrive Project

www.copperalliance.org

fernando.nuno@copperalliance.eu

UNIVERSITÀ
DEGLI STUDI
DELL'AQUILA

<https://univaq.it/>

marco.villani@univaq.it

giuseppe.fabri@univaq.it

www.refreedrive.eu

LinkedIn

<https://www.linkedin.com/company/electric-drivetrain-innovation-cluster/>

ReFreeDrive Project

Visit us

We'll be pleased to show you
RFD prototypes:
Booth 08C08

